

Goal Orientation and Task Difficulty toward Teachers' Professional Learning Activities and Performance: A Moderated Mediation Analysis

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ABSTRACT: This study on the goal orientation and task difficulty toward teachers' professional learning activities and performance: a moderated mediation analysis was undertaken to determine the extent teachers engage in professional learning activities at work; the perception of the respondents on teacher's performance; the perception of the respondents on goal orientation of the teachers at work; and the description of the respondents on the level of difficulty of their task in school. Furthermore, this study determined whether the goal orientation of the teachers significantly mediating the relationship between professional learning activities-at-work and their performance and whether the task difficulty significantly moderate the relationship between professional learning activities at work and teachers' performance. The study employed the descriptive with mediation analysis of research with 188 teachers used as the respondents of the study chosen through random sampling technique. A questionnaire was held with teachers and the collected data were analyzed using standard statistics.

The results show that the teacher-respondents always engage in professional activities at work, they have positive perception on their performance, they also have positive perception on their goal orientation at work, and they described that they did not find difficulty in doing their task in school. There is a significant relationship between professional learning activities at work and goal orientation of the teachers. There is a significant relationship between professional learning activities at work and teacher's performance. Goal orientation of teachers is a significant mediator in the relationship between professional learning activities at work and teacher performance. Constructs of task difficulty significantly moderate the relationship between professional learning activities at work and teacher performance.

KEYWORDS: Professional Learning Activities, Teachers Performance, Goal Orientation

INTRODUCTION

Educators play a key part in the process of constructing a nation. By employing competent educators, the Philippines can cultivate well-rounded students who possess strong moral principles, advanced skills relevant to the modern era, and the ability to drive the nation toward growth and advancement. This aligns with the Department of Education's objective of generating: "Filipinos who passionately love their country and whose values and competencies enable them to realize their full potential and contribute meaningfully to building the nation" (DepED Order No. 36, s. 2013).

Teachers, however, must possess the necessary qualifications to instruct students, so guaranteeing that these skills will be utilized in the future. Simultaneously, teachers must be equipped to handle a more diverse student population in their classrooms, which entails assuming additional responsibilities. Additionally, they must be prepared for increased societal demands placed on schools as a whole (OECD 2005). This emphasizes the need to enhance the skills and knowledge of instructors through professional development. In this article, professional development is described as the process by which teachers gain the necessary information, abilities, and values to enhance the quality of service they deliver to their clients.

Hoyle and John's, (1995). As Bob Garmston and Bruce Wellman (1998, as cited in Stoll, 2024) note, "Like the queen on a chessboard, the teacher with the most moves has the most options and the greatest degree of influence."

The teacher is the most crucial agent in the teaching and learning process. Teachers have the power to shape or undo their students' futures. Professional development can be strengthened through faculty development activities such as instructional planning, instructional delivery, subject matter expertise, rapport with students, and classroom management. In the twenty-first century, teaching practices are becoming more innovative and collaborative (Nairz-Wirth & Feldmann, 2019, as cited in Padillo, 2021).

Moreover, teachers must continuously adjust to the evolving changes in the educational system in order to fulfill the needs and requirements of students in the global market. (Padillo, 2021). Cansoy (2022) states that according to different studies, teachers, on

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the other hand, differ significantly in the extent to which individuals participate in both formal and informal learning activities obtaining knowledge, attending workshops within or beyond the school premises, and soliciting feedback. The goal orientation of teachers is closely associated with their motivation to engage in professional learning activities.

Engaging in professional learning activities enhances teachers' knowledge, skills, and performance, hence positively impacting their students' learning. Improving the caliber of teachers has become crucial for ensuring student success; the importance of teacher professionalism has increased. Currently, the ongoing professional development of instructors is widely recognized as essential for improving teachers' overall performance and effectiveness, as well as increasing their commitment to their work. Furthermore, teachers are required to participate in professional learning activities since the demands on both students and teachers in our knowledge society continue to rise. Students must possess the skills necessary to adapt to the demands of a knowledge and technology-driven society in the twenty-first century (Voogt and Roblin 2012). In addition, Rex and Jurasaitė-Harbison (2010) noted the significance of informal teacher learning in the classroom for teachers' professional growth and career long-term development. Postholm (2012) asserts that the ideal strategy for teachers continued professional development is classroom instruction. To be more specific, teachers must find creative ways to continue their professional development in the classroom if they want to alter how they go about doing their jobs. Hence, they not only fulfill the make the most of the limited resources available while also meeting the demand for teacher education. In light of this, it would seem useful to increase our empirical knowledge of the workplace professional development of teachers.

Also, an examination of background factors revealed that age, gender, and work experience outside of the field of education were associated with the various goal orientation profiles. Goal orientation profiles help elucidate the variations among teachers in their inclination to participate in professional development endeavors.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objective of this study was to determine how goal-oriented teachers can engage in continuing education initiatives, and how professional learning activities and task difficulty affect teachers' performance. Furthermore, by tying goal orientation to information acquisition and asking for feedback, this study added to the literature on teacher professional development. As a result, by examining the importance of goal orientation in professional development, this research added to our understanding of teachers' motivation for professional growth (Butler, 2007, as cited in George & Richardson, 2019). School leaders can use this information to create professional development policies that encourage certain groups of teachers to participate in professional learning activities.

Teachers engage in professional development to enhance their knowledge and skills, as well as to keep their practice current and critical. Teachers are more likely to inspire pupils and give high-quality teaching and learning experiences when they engage in a variety of high-quality, prolonged professional learning activities, allowing learners to attain their full potential.

Professional learning should provide extensive opportunities for teachers to build and expand their professional knowledge and practice to increase learning and teaching quality and school improvement.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study employed the descriptive with mediation analysis of research in determining the relationship between goal orientation and task difficulty to teachers, professional learning activities and performance, a moderated mediation analysis.

Descriptive research involves asking specific questions that guide the researchers in determining the approach needed to assess the topic accurately. This type of research focuses on what has happened rather than how or why it happened. Therefore, researchers often use observation and survey tools to collect data (Gall et al., 2007, as cited in Nassaji, 2015).

The study used a descriptive and correlational approach as it focuses on the current condition wherein events will be recorded, described, analyzed, and compared. The researcher-made online and pen-and-paper test survey questionnaire was used as the primary tool to collect data. The questionnaire is divided into five parts (respondent's profile, perceptions about goal orientation of teachers, perceptions about task difficulty, perceptions about teacher's professional learning activities-at-work, and perceptions about teacher's performance).

Respondents of the Study

The study was conducted in the secondary schools of Atimonan 1 and 2 District, situated in the municipality of Atimonan, province of Quezon. There were 188 respondents, which serve as population of teachers currently employed at seven public secondary schools in Atimonan 1 and 2 Districts, Division of Quezon. Respondents were described based on their age, gender, educational attainment, and length of teaching experience.

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Research Instrument

The researcher used a self-designed online and paper-based survey questionnaire as the primary tool for collecting data and information regarding the goal orientation and task difficulty to teachers professional learning activities and teacher's performance. This method is used to simplify the data gathering.

Construction. To determine the connection between goal-oriented teachers, task difficulties, and professional learning activities and performance, the researcher crafted an online survey questionnaire divided into five parts: respondent profile, perception about goal orientation, task difficulty, professional learning activities, and teacher performance.

Respondent Profile. This part deals with the respondent's profile including the name, age, gender, and work experience.

Part I. Professional Learning Activities-at-Work. This accords with the respondent's perception about teachers professional learning activities-at-work which includes keep up-to- date, experimenting, reflecting and asking feedback, collaboration to improve lessons, and collaboration for school development.

Part II. Teachers Performance. This concerns the respondent's perception of teachers' performance. This includes content knowledge and pedagogy, diversity of learners, assessment and reporting, curriculum and planning, community linkages and professional engagement, personal growth and professional development.

Part III. Goal Orientation of Teachers. This pertains to the respondent's perception of his or her goal orientation at work.

Part IV. Task Difficulty. This is about the respondent's perception of his or her task difficulties at work.

Validation. To ensure the consistency and accuracy of the survey questionnaire, the researcher presented it to the thesis adviser and other panel members for correction and suggestions on its enhancement. To test for the reliability, this research utilized Cronbach's rule of thumb for interpreting.

Statistical Treatment

The following were the statistical measures to be used in the study.

To examine the support given or extended by the teachers in public secondary schools through teachers professional learning activities at work, mean and standard deviation were computed. Likewise, in describing the level of the work performance of teacherrespondents of the school, was assessed by calculating the mean and standard deviation.

To prove the hypotheses set in the study whether professional learning and goal orientation of teachers are significantly related by the professional learning activities and teachers' performance, Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was employed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The tabulated data and the results of the study were presented, the corresponding analysis as well as the interpretation of the data as a result of the statistical treatment used.

Table 1. Extent of Teachers' Engagement in Professional Learning Activities at Work as to Keeping Up-to-Date

Statements As teacher, I...	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. study different literature related to my subject matter.	3.57	0.54	Always
2. visit educational sites on the internet.	3.60	0.56	Always
3. read educational/subject matter pedagogical literature.	3.55	0.58	Always
4. participate in a one-day conference or study day that centers around subject matter pedagogy.	3.25	0.67	Often
5. participate in a training course that centers around subject matter pedagogy.	3.43	0.61	Often
Overall	3.48	0.46	Often

Legend: 1.00-1.49 (Never); 1.50-2.49 (Sometimes); 2.50-3.49 (Often); 3.50-4.00 (Always).

Table 1 shows the mean extent teachers engage in professional learning activities at work as to keeping up-to-date. It shows that teachers often engage in professional learning activities at work with an average mean of 3.48. Meanwhile, visiting educational sites on the internet has the highest mean of 3.60; while participating in a one-day conference or study day that centers around subject matter pedagogy has the lowest mean of 3.25.

The result also indicates that teacher is always engaged in visiting educational site on the internet, studying different literature related to their subject matter and reading educational/subject matter pedagogical literature to keep them up to date, but they often engaged in participating in a training course that centers around subject matter pedagogy and participating in a one-day conference or study day that centers around subject matter pedagogy.

This study is supported with Geijsel, et al., (2009) when the mentioned that, teachers, for example, keep up-to-date by reading educational literature and researching subject field literature. In addition, Shatri, et al., (2021) found that teachers' attitudes regarding using the platform in their instruction are good, which helps make the lessons easier for the teachers to teach and more engaging for the students. Moreover, Ephraim (2023) enumerated seven ways in which teachers can stay up-todate with the latest education

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research and two of them are by engaging in online communities and forums and by following educational research institutions and experts on social media. He mentioned that there are online communities and forums specifically designed for educators to discuss and share research-based practices. Participating in these communities allows teachers to interact with peers, exchange ideas, and learn about the latest research in education. In addition, following educational research institutions and experts on social media: Many educational research institutions, universities, and experts have a social media presence. By following them on platforms like Twitter or LinkedIn, teachers can receive updates, research articles, and insights directly in their feed. By actively seeking out and engaging with these resources and opportunities, teachers can stay informed about the latest education research and incorporate evidence-based practices into their teaching methodologies.

Table 2. Extent of Teachers' Engagement in Professional Learning Activities at Work as to Experimenting

Statements <i>As teacher, I...</i>	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. try out new teaching methods in my lesson.	3.60	0.53	Always
2. try out new applications of ICT in my lesson.	3.49	0.60	Often
3. test alternative teaching materials in class.	3.49	0.63	Often
4. apply and evaluate other forms of assessment.	3.54	0.55	Always
5. inquire about new teaching methods in class.	3.57	0.62	Always
Overall	3.54	0.47	Always

Legend: 1.00-1.49 (Never); 1.50-2.49 (Sometimes); 2.50-3.49 (Often); 3.50-4.00 (Always).

Table 2 presents the mean extent teachers engage in professional learning activities at work as to experimenting. With an average mean of 3.54, it implicates that teachers are always engaged in professional learning activities at work as to experimenting. Trying out new teaching methods in their lessons has the highest mean of 3.60 while trying out new applications of ICT in my lesson and testing alternative teaching materials in class have the lowest mean of 3.49.

Modern teaching methods are designed to make learning more engaging, interactive, and relevant to students. They provide students with the opportunity to take an active role in their learning, develop the skills they need to succeed in the 21st century and meet the diverse needs of the student population. Adopting modern teaching methods in schools is crucial for ensuring that students receive a high-quality education that prepares them for the future. It's important that teachers are trained on diverse methodologies and can create a classroom environment that is inclusive, diverse, and culturally responsive to all students (Edutinker, 2023). Similarly, Kampen (2021) mentioned that when teachers try new teaching methods and flex their approach, every student benefits. It keeps them engaged. Moreover, according to Main (2022), an effective teacher applies the most innovative and creative teaching methods to teach academic concepts and meet the individual needs of students.

Teachers try out new teaching methods in their lesson for the students to learn more effectively. They choose the method that are suitable for their student's and for the topic that he is going to discuss.

Table 3. Extent of Teachers' Engagement in Professional Learning Activities at Work as to Reflecting and Asking Feedback

Statements <i>As a teacher, I...</i>	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. ask pupils for feedback on the way I teach.	3.38	0.66	Often
2. reflect on the different educational applications of ICT.	3.40	0.61	Often
3. reflect on my strong and weak points.	3.50	0.59	Always
4. invite colleagues to attend my lesson.	2.98	0.87	Often
5. adapt teaching methods in response to pupils' reactions.	3.55	0.60	Always
Overall	3.36	0.51	Often

Legend: 1.00-1.49 (Never); 1.50-2.49 (Sometimes); 2.50-3.49 (Often); 3.50-4.00 (Always).

Table 3 presents the mean extent teachers engage in professional learning activities at work as to reflecting and asking feedback. With an overall mean of 3.36, teachers often engaged in professional learning activities at work as to reflecting and feedback. Teachers' engagement on adapting teaching methods in response to pupils' reaction has the highest mean of 3.55 while their engagement on inviting colleagues to attend their lesson has the lowest mean of 2.98. Furthermore, the study also shows that teachers are always engaged on reflecting on their strong and weak points and they are often engaged on asking pupils for feedback on the way they teach and reflecting on the different educational applications of ICT.

Adaptive teaching is thought to be essential to both student learning and the quality of instruction. It explains how educators modify their lessons to meet the various requirements and comprehension levels of their pupils (Hardy, et al. 2022).

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Furthermore, teachers also reflect on their strong and weak points. Teachers and students can become more aware of their strengths and weaknesses when they conduct self-reflection. It will lead to meaningful change in the classroom environment. Teachers who practice self-reflection can assess their present methods, identify areas that require development, and implement the required adjustments to enhance student performance. (Datta, 2023). In addition, a vital component of professional development is teacher self-reflection, which aids instructors in refining their methods and advancing student learning. According to a study that was published in the Journal of Educational Psychology, teachers who practiced self-reflection were more likely to identify their own strengths and weakness and, as a result, modify their methods in order to enhance the learning outcomes for their students. Through reflection, educators can assess their techniques, identify their strengths and weaknesses, and create practical plans to address areas that need work (GoReact, 2024).

Table 4. Extent teachers engage in professional learning activities at work as to: Collaboration to Improve Lessons

Statements As a teacher, I...	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. discuss teaching approaches with colleagues.	3.38	0.63	Often
2. discuss lessons with colleagues in using technological platforms.	3.30	0.68	Often
3. use peer coaching when experience teaching problems.	3.39	0.64	Often
4. prepare lessons with colleagues.	3.18	0.76	Often
5. make agreements with colleagues about the pedagogical practices.	3.27	0.73	Often
Overall	3.30	0.59	Often

Legend: 1.00-1.49 (Never); 1.50-2.49 (Sometimes); 2.50-3.49 (Often); 3.50-4.00 (Always).

Table 4 presents the mean extent teachers engage in professional learning activities at work in terms of collaboration to improve lessons. With an average mean of 3.30, it indicates that teachers are often engaged in collaboration to improve lessons. Engagement on using peer coaching when experience teaching problems has the highest mean of 3.39 while engagement on preparing lessons with colleagues has the lowest mean of 3.18. Furthermore, the result also shows that teachers are often engaged on the following professional learning activities: discussing teaching approaches with colleagues; discussing lessons with colleagues in using technological platforms and making agreements with colleagues about the pedagogical practices.

This study was supported by one of the authors in digital promise. He/She mentioned that to effectively meet the needs of their students, create beneficial connections, and identify areas of subject and teaching methodology overlap, educators—teachers, coaches, and other staff members—need time to work together and learn from one another. However, scheduling time for teachers to meet together can be challenging for schools, whether it's for formal Professional Learning Communities (PLCs) development, common planning time, or co-teaching. While PLCs can offer venues for fruitful dialogue and action regarding instructional approaches, creating or finding formalized engagement norms for teacher collaboration requires initial and ongoing support, time, and effort from facilitators. Moreover, this study was also related to the study conducted by Torgerson, (2022). He found out that assisting students is a teacher's primary objective. Teachers have challenging jobs, especially when a pupil is having difficulty or when they have tried all strategies for the learner to show engagement. Additionally, he mentioned that teacher collaboration at work enables educators to pool their minds to discuss students' challenges and come up with fresh ideas for how to support them. It is not surprising that teamwork can boost test scores, enhance student engagement, increase graduation rates, and even increase college enrollment when numerous people are together to improve student outcomes.

There is a need for teachers to engage in professional activities specifically collaboration because in the year of 2021, Johnson and LaFollette found that informal conversations with coworkers at lunch or during after-school gatherings can foster professional development. Furthermore, a study by Borko and Putnam (2018) emphasized the value of peer cooperation as a non-formal activity for enhancing instructional strategies (Rani, 2023).

Table 5. Extent teachers engage in professional learning activities at work as to Collaboration for School Development

Statements As a teacher, I...	MEAN	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. discuss ideas about educational improvement and innovation in my school with colleagues.	3.40	0.65	Often
2. discuss school organizational matters with colleagues using technological platforms.	3.30	0.68	Often
3. think about the design and method of colleagues.	3.35	0.63	Often
4. assemble a school working group or committee with colleagues.	3.27	0.65	Often

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5. give an opinion together with colleagues about school organizational matters to the school management.	3.43	0.65	Often
Overall	3.35	0.56	Often

Legend: 1.00-1.49 (Never); 1.50-2.49 (Sometimes); 2.50-3.49 (Often); 3.50-4.00 (Always).

Table 5 presents the mean extent teachers engage in professional learning activities at work in terms of collaboration for school development. With a mean average of 3.35, it shows that teachers are often engaged in collaboration for school development. Furthermore, teachers' engagement on giving an opinion together with colleagues about school organizational matters to the school management has the highest mean of 3.43 while teachers' engagement on assembling a school working group or committee with colleagues has the lowest mean of 3.27.

The ability to collaborate and be organized is essential for being a teacher leader. It is essential to have collaborative skills such as sharing responsibility, resolving conflicts, modeling, and adapting language to the context. Teacher leaders' organizational abilities enable them to collaborate with success as well (Arizona, K12 Center, 2021).

Teachers use collaboration strategies that are linked to a negligible loss of their personal autonomy. Teachers who collaborate also perceive benefits, and teachers who feel pressurized by the principal to collaborate neither collaborate more nor perceive more benefits to collaboration. Reviewing all the data with an emphasis on school development procedures, practical suggestions are made (Muckenthaler, et. al. 2020). In order for school development to benefit teachers and improve the school overall, it is necessary to offer opportunities for action and foster collaboration. At the same time, instructors must have room for their own professional growth. Moreover, the same holds true for actions taken to integrate collaboration into classrooms (Huber, 2004).

Table 6. Summary of the extent of teachers' engagement in professional learning activities at work

Statements	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Keep up-to-date.	3.48	0.46	Moderately Engaged
2. Experimenting	3.54	0.47	Highly Engaged
3. Reflecting and Asking for Feedback	3.36	0.51	Moderately Engaged
4. Collaboration to improve lessons	3.30	0.59	Moderately Engaged
5. Collaboration for school development	3.35	0.56	Moderately Engaged
Overall	3.41	0.52	Moderately Engaged

Legend: 1.00-1.49 (Not Engaged); 1.50-2.49 (Fairly Engaged); 2.50-3.49 (Moderately Engaged); 3.50-4.00 (Highly Engaged).

Table 6 shows the summary of extent teachers engage in professional learning activities-at-work. It shows that with an overall mean of 3.41, it indicates that respondents are moderately engaged in professional learning activities at work. Meanwhile, they are highly engaged only in terms of experimenting with the highest overall mean of 3.41. On the other hand, teachers' engagement on collaboration to improve lessons has the lowest overall mean of 3.30 which indicate that they are moderately engaged in this professional activity. They are also moderately engaged on keeping up-to-date, reflecting and asking for feedback and collaboration for school development.

The result shows that there is a need for teacher to be highly engaged in different professional learning activities. One of the authors in WordPress.com (2015) mentioned that in order for teachers to remain effective over the years, they must keep up-to-date with constant changes in educational research, development and policy. Moreover, teachers who take time daily to reflect on what worked in class and what didn't can better assess areas for improvement and begin to make necessary adjustments (Collins 2021). Informal discussions with colleagues during lunch breaks or after-school meetings can contribute to professional growth (Johnson and LaFollette, 2021, as cited by Rani 2023). Peer collaboration is an informal activity for improving teaching practices (Borko and Putnam, 2018). Coburn and Penuel (2020) emphasized the benefits of engaging in personal reading, researching online materials, blogs or participating in social media groups as informal avenues for continuous learning.

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Table 7. Perception of the Respondents on Teachers' Performance with Regard to Content and Knowledge and Pedagogy

Statements As teacher, I...	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. apply knowledge of content within and across the curriculum teaching areas	3.76	0.44	Strongly Agree
2. use a range of teaching strategies that enhance learner achievement in literacy and numeracy skills	3.77	0.43	Strongly Agree
3. apply a range of teaching strategies to develop critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills	3.70	0.48	Strongly Agree
Overall	3.74	0.39	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.49 (Strongly Disagree); 1.50-2.49 (Disagree); 2.50-3.49 (Agree); 3.50-4.00 (Strongly Agree).

Table 7 shows the mean perception of the respondents on teacher's performance with regard to content, knowledge, and pedagogy. With an overall mean of 3.74, indicates that teachers have a strong agreement on their performance with regard to content, knowledge and pedagogy. It also shows that using a range of teaching strategies that enhance learner achievement in literacy and numeracy skills has the highest average mean of 3.77 while applying a range of teaching strategies to develop critical and creative thinking, as well as other higher-order thinking skills has the lowest mean of 3.70 but still there is a strong agreement in this performance.

The result of this study is supported with the study conducted by Manigbas III, et. al. (2024). The results of their study revealed that teachers are highly competent in content knowledge and pedagogy. As the policy and guidelines released by the Department of Education under DepEd Order No. 35 s. 2016, content and pedagogy of the K to 12 Basic Education Program should be mastered by the teacher. Content and performance standards and learning competencies must be mastered by teachers so that they can plan lessons, deliver instruction effectively, and assess the learning that resulted from their teaching. In addition, pedagogical content knowledge is the ability of a teacher to help students understand a particular subject. This knowledge includes knowing how specific subject matter topics, problems, and issues can be organized, represented, and tailored to the various interests and skills of learners before being presented for instruction. The idea of pedagogical content knowledge as the outcome of the transformation of information from other domains is its distinguishing characteristic (Borko, et al. (1999).

Table 8. Perception of the Respondents on Teachers' Performance with Regard to Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners

Statements As teacher, I...	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. manage classroom structure to engage learners, individually or in groups, in meaningful exploration, discovery, and hands-on activities within a range of physical learning environments.	3.78	0.43	Strongly Agree
2. manage learner behavior constructively by applying positive and non-violent discipline to ensure learning-focused environments.	3.74	0.45	Strongly Agree
3. use differentiated, developmentally appropriate learning experiences to address the learner's gender, needs, strengths, interests, and experiences.	3.73	0.46	Strongly Agree
Overall	3.75	0.39	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.49 (Strongly Disagree); 1.50-2.49 (Disagree); 2.50-3.49 (Agree); 3.50-4.00 (Strongly Agree).

Table 8 shows the mean perception of the respondents on teacher's performance with regard to learning environment and diversity of learners. It has an average mean of 3.75 which implicates that respondents strongly agree on their perception with regard to a learning environment and diversity of learners. Teachers' perception on managing classroom structure to engage learners, individually or in groups, in meaningful exploration, discovery, and hands-on activities within a range of physical learning environments has the highest mean of 3.78 while perception on using differentiated, developmentally appropriate learning experiences to address the learner's gender, needs, strengths, interests, and experiences has the lowest mean of 3.73. They also strongly agree on their perception on managing learner behavior constructively by applying positive and nonviolent discipline to ensure learning-focused environments.

Because it is a crucial part of classroom management that supports both teaching and learning, classroom setup is an important element of a learning environment. The physical environment of the classroom can support and enhance learning while also assisting in the prevention of behavioral problems. For both teachers and students, the way the learning environment is structured is crucial. A well-structured classroom management plan of design has the power to enhance behavior and learning. The physical layout of the classroom can influence the conduct of both teachers and students. Using classroom management, including how your desks are

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arranged, is important for creating a welcoming, secure, and encouraging learning atmosphere. Having a positive learning atmosphere can make all the difference in the world to how your day goes (Cox, 2019).

Classroom learning settings need to be adaptable to meet the demands of a wide range of students in order to be effective for all of them. These varied needs include developmental stages, academic preparedness, learning styles, and cultural and language variances. All students are engaged in a responsive learning environment because it fosters a respectful environment where curriculum and instruction are tailored to each student's requirements and background.

Teachers need to confront and embrace living and working in a diverse country as we help kids be ready for college or the workforce. Children learn to appreciate diverse viewpoints in the classroom through diversity, which is a lifelong learning. But a lot of teachers have trouble with this because they don't even know what diversity in the classroom looks like. Brown outlined a few methods for beginning to diversity the classroom. Teachers include diverse learning and teaching material; support students in differing viewpoints; get to know their students; connect with parents and the community; and celebrate diversity by acknowledging it and allowing children to celebrate it at school (Staff, 2008).

Table 9. Perception of the Respondents on Teacher's Performance with Regard to Curriculum and Planning

Statements <i>As teacher, I...</i>	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. plan, manage, and implement developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes to meet curriculum requirements and varied teaching contexts	3.71	0.47	Strongly Agree
2. participate in collegial discussions that use teacher and learner feedback to enrich teaching practice.	3.56	0.53	Strongly Agree
3. select, develop, organize, and use appropriate teaching and learning resources, including ICT, to address learning goals.	3.65	0.49	Strongly Agree
Overall	3.64	0.41	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.49 (Strongly Disagree); 1.50-2.49 (Disagree); 2.50-3.49 (Agree); 3.50-4.00 (Strongly Agree)

Table 9 presents the perception of the respondents on teacher's performance with regard to curriculum and planning. It has an average mean of 3.64 which indicates that teachers have strong agreement on their performance with regard curriculum planning. Teachers' perception on planning, managing, and implementing developmentally sequenced teaching and learning processes to meet curriculum requirements and varied teaching contexts has the highest mean of 3.71, however, teachers' perception on participating in collegial discussions that use teacher and learner feedback to enrich teaching practice has the lowest mean of 3.56.

Effective planning has a positive relationship with teaching and learning (Innocent, 2021). Moreover, the curriculum is designed to direct the teacher's pedagogical practice, considering school actions such as planning, assessing, and other activities that the teacher develops in the classroom. In order to attain these goals, the instructor must be able to oversee the curriculum's development and choose its essential subjects. Therefore, in order to plan the curriculum, in order to develop pedagogical methods, it is imperative to pay attention to the conditions of teaching both inside and outside of the school environment. Given that the purpose of the instructor is to plan or predict learning in teaching, rather than merely disseminating the objectives for students to analyze or study. Finally, it is necessary that the materials that need to be learned in the classroom are organized methodologically to provide conditions that are favorable to the effectiveness of the teaching and learning process (Nogueira, 2020).

Table 10. Perception of the Respondents on Teacher's Performance with Regard to Assessment and Reporting

Statements <i>As teacher, I...</i>	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. design, select, organize, and use diagnostic, formative, and summative assessment strategies consistent with curriculum requirements	3.73	0.45	Strongly Agree
2. monitor and evaluate learner progress and achievement using learner attainment data.	3.76	0.43	Strongly Agree
3. communicate promptly and clearly the learners' needs, progress, and achievement to key stakeholders, including parents/guardians .	3.73	0.46	Strongly Agree
Overall	3.74	0.37	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.0-1.49 (Strongly Disagree); 1.50-2.49 (Disagree); 2.50-3.49 (Agree); 3.50-4.00 (Strongly Agree)

Table 10 presents the perception of the respondents on teacher's performance with regard to assessment and reporting. With an overall average mean of 3.74, teachers a strong agreement on their perception with regard to assessment and reporting. Monitoring and evaluating learner progress and achievement using learner attainment data has the highest mean of 3.76. Perception on designing, selecting, organizing, and using diagnostic, formative, and summative assessment strategies consistent with curriculum requirements; and communicating promptly and clearly the learners' needs, progress, and achievement to key stakeholders, including parents/guardians have the lowest mean of 3.73.

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Assessment benefits teachers in the same way that it benefits students. Additionally, it enables instructors to make sure that students get the knowledge necessary to fulfill the learning objectives of the course.

British Columbia (2020) mentioned that an essential component of education is classroom assessment, which can provide valuable insights into students' learning. For students, immediate and personalized feedback from continuing assessments in the classroom can help them recognize their misconceptions and utilize that knowledge to create new learning objectives. Making sure parents are aware of their children's progress is the aim of reporting and communicating student learning. Student achievement is largely dependent on the home and school having effective communication. Ensuring and enhancing efficient procedures for documenting and sharing student learning guarantees that parents and students will be informed about the student's development promptly and effectively.

Monitoring student progress is a crucial aspect of education, and it involves more than just the students. Teachers receive important information about their students' growth and accomplishments through regular, official and informal assessments. Furthermore, tracking students' development allows teachers to evaluate the effectiveness of their educational tactics and reflect on their own teaching. (Victoria, 2022). One of the most powerful tools that teachers use in the classroom is assessment data. How teachers use this data is a crucial component of their instruction. It is necessary to gather, assess, and utilize data for student interventions and education. Student learning will be optimally impacted by understanding how to use assessment data (Diaz, 2023).

Table 11. Perception of the Respondents on Teacher's Performance with Regard to Personal Growth and Professional Development

Statements	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
As teacher, I...			
1. apply a personal philosophy of teaching that is learner-centered	3.72	0.45	Strongly Agree
2. set professional development goals based on the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers.	3.69	0.46	Strongly Agree
Overall	3.70	0.41	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.0-1.49 (Strongly Disagree); 1.50-2.49 (Disagree); 2.50-3.49 (Agree); 3.50-4.00 (Strongly Agree)

Table 11 presents the perception of the respondents with regard to personal growth and professional development. It has an average mean of 3.70 which indicates that teachers have a strong agreement on their perception with regard to personal growth and development. Moreover, applying a personal philosophy of teaching that is learner-centered has the highest mean of 3.72 and setting professional development goals based on the Philippine Professional standards for teachers has the lowest mean of 3.69.

The most potent and successful way to raise learners' demands and enable them to obtain the resources they need to meet their learning objectives is through professional development. Professional development influences teachers' methods in the classroom and raises students' academic performance. As a result of compelling CPD experiences, instructors are motivated by continuous professional development to enhance their teaching competencies in order to better fulfill the needs of learners in accordance with educational demands (Qadir, et al. 2020).

The result of the study is supported by personal philosophy of teaching of Tuga-on (2023) that is learner centered. As a high school teacher, her philosophy revolves around learner-centered education, where students are at the heart of the learning process. She believed that education should be a transformative experience that empowers students to develop their full potential both academically and personally.

Table 12. Summary of the Perception of the Respondents on Teacher's Performance

Statements	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Content, Knowledge and Pedagogy	3.74	0.39	Very Satisfactory
2. Diversity of Learners, Assessment and Reporting	3.75	0.39	Very Satisfactory
3. Curriculum and Planning	3.64	0.41	Very Satisfactory
4. Assessment and Reporting	3.74	0.37	Very Satisfactory
5. Community Linkages, Professional Engagement, Personal Growth and Professional Development	3.70	0.41	Very Satisfactory
Overall	3.71	0.40	Very Satisfactory

Legend: 1.0(Agree/Satisfactory)-1.49 (Strongly Disagree); 3.50-4.00 (Strongly Agree/Needs Improvement/Very Satisfactory); 1.50-2.49 (). Disagree/Unsatisfactory); 2.50-3.49

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Table 12 presents the summary of the perception of the respondents on teacher's performance. With an overall average mean of 3.71, it indicates that the respondents perceived that they have a very satisfactory performance. Teachers' perception on their performance with regard to learning environment and diversity of learners, has the highest average mean of 3.75 while teachers' perception on their performance with regard to curriculum and planning has the lowest mean of 3.64. Moreover, teachers have a very satisfactory performance in all the domain listed.

The result of the study was supported by the study of Dela Rosa and Vargas (2021). They found out that in their study on performance of teachers relative to the five components of teaching, classroom management component was rated the highest among the five components of teaching. This component received an overall mean rating of 8.50 hence, describing teachers as having a very satisfactory performance in managing a class. In point of ranking, it was in the component of classroom management where the general education teachers obtained the highest mean rating as compared with the other ratings obtained in the four remaining components (8.16, classroom management; 8.12, assessment of learning; 8.10, methods and techniques of teaching; 8.08, mastery of the subject matter; and 7.86, planning and organization).

Table 13. Perception of the Respondents on Goal Orientation of the Teachers at Work

As teacher, I...	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. goal to achieve to demonstrate understanding, academic competence or improved performance relative to self-established standards	3.72	0.46	Strongly Agree
2. goal to ensure that my students will achieve to enhance a sense of belonging to their groups.	3.74	0.45	Strongly Agree
3. goal to achieve academically to be able to assist others in their academic or personal development	3.72	0.45	Strongly Agree
4. desire to learn things for school, to arrange them so that I can understand them better	3.67	0.47	Strongly Agree
5. goal to use various methods, techniques, and strategies that support learning in the classroom	3.68	0.51	Strongly Agree
6. goal to teach based on the level of the pupils	3.71	0.47	Strongly Agree
7. goal to believe that they are efficient, consistent in trying harder, being more willing to teach, and being more open to change and adaptation	3.70	0.47	Strongly Agree
8. desire to create learning-centered classes	3.74	0.45	Strongly Agree
Overall	3.71	0.36	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.0-1.49 (Strongly Disagree); 1.50-2.49 (Disagree); 2.50-3.49 (Agree); 3.50-4.00 (Strongly Agree).

Table 13 shows the perception of the respondents on goal orientation of the teachers at work. With an average mean of 3.71 and a descriptive rating of strongly agree, it indicates that the respondents have a very high goal orientation at work. Moreover, the perception that it is the goal of teachers to ensure that their students will achieve to enhance a sense of belonging to their groups and their desire to create learning-centered classes have the highest mean of 3.74 while the perception that it is the goal of teachers to desire to learn things for school, to arrange them so that he/she can understand them better has the lowest mean of 3.67.

According to Gray, as cited by Bowen (2021), in many ways, a sense of belonging in the classroom can boost students' academic performance and motivational results. Teachers can foster this feeling of belonging by fostering relationships between the classroom and the community.

Students who have a strong sense of belonging are more likely to succeed academically and to be happy. According to research, kids who feel like they belong are more likely to perform better academically, stay in school longer, and have lower absentee rates. Students who have a high sense of belonging in school generally put in more effort and are more motivated at school. Schools offer a unique environment for students to develop their sense of belonging. A sense of belonging is particularly important during periods

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of transition, including primary to secondary school and post-school transitions. Pupils who grow up in a loving, supportive school where they feel like they belong have a great foundation for succeeding academically. The social and organizational culture of a school can give children the nurturing environment they need to grow into people who feel like they belong in the community outside of school (Halcrow, 2020).

Table 14. Description of the Respondents on the Level of Difficulty of their Task in School

Statements <i>As teacher, I...</i>	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretatio
1. apply mastery of content knowledge and its application across learning areas	1.69	.70	Disagree
2. facilitate learning using appropriate and innovative teaching strategies and classroom management practices.	1.66	.69	Disagree
3. manage an environment conducive to learning	1.74	.78	Disagree
4. address learner diversity	1.92	.82	Disagree
5. implement and supervise curricular and cocurricular programs to support learning	1.76	.67	Disagree
6. monitor and evaluate learner progress and undertake activities to improve learner performance	1.62	.72	Disagree
7. maintain updated records of learners' progress	1.58	.69	Disagree
8. counsel and guide learners	1.65	.72	Disagree
9. work with relevant stakeholders, both internal and external, to promote learning and improve school performance	1.92	.84	Disagree
10. undertake activities towards personal and professional growth	1.62	.66	Disagree
11. perform tasks related to professional and personal functions	1.49	.63	Strongly Disagree
Overall	1.70	.49	Disagree

Legend: 1.0-1.49 (Strongly Disagree); 1.50-2.49 (Disagree); 2.50-3.49 (Agree); 3.50-4.00 (Strongly Agree).

Table 14 presents the description of the respondents on the level of difficulty of their task in school. With an average mean of 1.70, it indicates that the respondents disagree that they find difficulty on their task in school. Moreover, performing task related to professional and personal functions has the lowest mean of 1.49 which indicates that the respondents strongly disagree that they find difficulty in doing this task.

On the study conducted by Metin (2021), he found out teachers encountered challenges such as crowded classrooms, insufficient time for assessment, inadequate learning environments, limited access to technology, and a lack of objective assessment.

In contrary, Nemenzo (2018) on her study,

“Problems Encountered by Teachers in Teaching Learning Process: A Basis of an Action Plan”, which aimed to identify the extent of problems encountered by teachers in relation to their performance in terms of Individual Performance and Review Form (IPCRF) found out that teachers encountered moderate challenges in creating functional lesson plans for daily instruction, extremely high challenges in the absence of personal laptops for educational purposes, and high challenges in the following areas: large class sizes, broken or obsolete computers, absenteeism, difficulty conceptualizing and following English-language classroom rules, bullying, work, indifferent students, lying, littering, student care, and contaminated shoes.

Table 15. Significant Relationship between Professional Learning activities-at-Work and Goal Orientation of the Teachers

Professional Learning Activities-At-Work	Goal Orientation of Teachers
Keep Up to date	.350**
Experimenting	.435**
Reflecting and asking for feedback	.313**
Collaboration to improve lessons	.147*
Collaboration for school development	.294**

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). *Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).
 Verbal Interpretation of r-value: +1.0 Perfect positive +/- association +0.8 to +1.0 Very strong +/- association +0.6 to +0.8 Strong +/- association +0.4 to +0.6 Moderate +/- association +0.2 to +0.4 Weak +/- association 0.0 to +0.2 Very weak +/- or no association

Table 15 presents the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient on finding the significant relationship between professional learning activities-atwork and goal orientation of the teachers. It shows that the absolute computed r-value in terms of keep up to date (.350), in experimenting, (0.435), in reflecting and asking for feedback is (0.313), in collaboration to improve lessons is (0.147) and in collaboration for school development is (0.294) is significant at 0.01 level. The result reveal that there is a significant

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relationship between professional learning activities-at-work and goal orientation of the teachers. It shows that a weak to moderate relationship was seen between variables.

A combination of high learning goals, high-performance approach goals, and low-performance avoidance goals (success-oriented profile) produced the highest mean score on both professional development activities, according to a relationship between the goal orientation profiles and professional development activities. This demonstrates that more engagement in professional development activities is linked to both a high learning goal orientation and the particular combination of high-performance approach goals. Teachers that possess a success-oriented profile are intent on comprehending assignments and prefer to work in demanding settings where they can study while also taking advantage of chances to demonstrate their abilities to others (Kunts, et al. 2018).

In addition, Sarigul (2021) in her study on the relationship between the teaching goal orientation and teaching approach of physical education and sports teachers found out that the critical role that these educators' instructional behaviors, approaches, and educational objectives play in the learning process. Students' learning of physical education and sports will be further enhanced by teachers' enrichment of their instruction through the development of a relationship between their goal orientations and instructional techniques towards teaching physical education and sports lessons. Regular in-service training will help physical education and sports teachers develop their teaching abilities, acquire new professional knowledge and skills, build better and more genuine relationships with their students, and accomplish the objectives of their lessons.

The Keep up-to-date, Experimenting, Reflecting and asking for feedback, Collaboration to improve lessons, Collaboration for school development, may, therefore, be encouraged when educators possess a profile that combines a performance-approach and a learning goal orientation.

Table 16. Significant Relationship Between Goal Orientation of the Teachers and Teachers' Performance

	Teacher's Performance				
	Content Knowledge	Learning Environment	Curriculum and Planning	Assessment and Reporting	Personal Growth and Development
Goal Orientation of Teachers	.566**	.569**	.535**	.521**	.624**

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Verbal Interpretation of r-value: +1.0 Perfect positive +/- association +0.8 to +1.0 Very strong +/- association +0.6 to +0.8 Strong +/- association +0.4 to +0.6 Moderate +/- association +0.2 to +0.4 Weak +/- association 0.0 to +0.2 Very weak +/- or no association

Table 16 presents the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient on finding the significant relationship between goal orientation of the teachers and teachers' performance. It shows that the absolute computed r-value in terms of content knowledge (0.566), learning environment (0.569), curriculum and planning (0.535) and assessment and reporting (0.521) and personal growth and development (0.624) which is significant at the 0.01 level indicates that there is a significant relationship between goal orientation of the teachers and their performance. A moderate to strong relationship was seen between variables.

As a result of the increased opportunity to enhance their knowledge, skills, and abilities, teachers with a high learning goal orientation are probably more engaged in the process of acquiring information (Janssen & Prins, 2007; Tuckey, Brewer, & Williamson, 2002;

Weiss, Lurie, & MacInnis, 2008 as cited in Kunts 2017).

On the other hand, teachers who have performance approach goals might only obtain information if they believe it will directly affect their performance or ability to meet expectations (Weiss et al., 2008 as cited in Kunts 2017). Conversely, teachers who score highly on performance avoidance would only obtain information in order to avoid coming across as incompetent to others. However, we are unaware of the ways in which a blend of different goal orientations influences information acquisition.

Table 17. Significant Relationship Between Professional Learning Activities-at-Work and Teachers' Performance

Professional Learning Activities-At-Work	Teacher's Performance				
	CK	LE	CP	AR	PG
Keep Up to date	.415**	.385**	.408**	.352**	.434**
Experimenting	.460**	.457**	.428**	.415**	.365**
Reflecting and asking for feedback	.345**	.408**	.338**	.294**	.309**
Collaboration to improve lessons	.281**	.309**	.293**	.266**	.269**
Collaboration for school development	.335**	.388**	.419**	.334**	.365**

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Verbal Interpretation of r-value: +1.0 Perfect positive +/- association +0.8 to +1.0 Very strong +/- association +0.6 to +0.8

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Strong +/-no association- association +0.4 to +0.6 Moderate +/- association +0.2 to +0.4 Weak +/- association 0.0 to +0.2 Very weak +/- or

Table 17 presents the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient on finding the significant relationship between professional learning activities-atwork and teachers' performance. It shows that the absolute computed r-value of the two variables is significant at the 0.01 level which implicates that there is a significant relationship among variables. A weak to moderate relationship was seen between variables.

In this connection, teacher's performance in the classroom in terms of the secondary school students' learning achievement has a moderate positive correlation with the curriculum preparation for learning that the teacher does (Huaranga, 2021). Additionally, in the research that Padillo et al. Al (2021), they discovered that professional development activities and teaching competencies do not significantly correlate. Contextual elements and individual perspectives were cited as the reasons behind the perceived benefits of professional development programs.

In the research that Rani et al. al. (2023) conducted, they discovered that learning activities have a strong beneficial influence on the professional development of teachers, which in turn results in better teaching methods, higher levels of student involvement, and better academic results. These revelations can guide the creation of successful policies and initiatives that support the professional development of teachers, which will have a significant impact on raising educational standards.

Table 18. Mediating Effect of Goal Orientation of Teachers on the Relationship Between Professional Learning Activities at Work and Teachers' Performance

Indirect Effects	Effect	SE	LLCI	ULCI
PLA→GOT→TP	.1447	.0376	.0820	.2293
Completely Standardized Indirect Effects				
PLA→GOT→TP	.1970	.0421	.1215	.2857

Legend: PLA (Professional Learning Activities -at-work); GOT (Goal Orientation of Teachers); TP (Teacher's Performance).

Table 18 shows the mediating effect of goal orientation of teachers to the relationship between professional learning activities-at-work and teachers' performance.

Mediation analyses were initiated using PROCESS Macro v4.1 following the procedure of Hayes (2022). Findings revealed that constructs of goal orientation of teachers could explain the variation of professional learning activities-at-work and teacher's performance. The results further showed that the overall goal orientation of teachers is a significant mediator in the relationship between professional learning activities at work and teacher performance. These indirect effects are statistically different from zero, as revealed by a biased-corrected bootstrap confidence interval based on 5,000 samples from the lower and upper limit class interval. The result indicates that the overall goal orientation of teachers can transmit the effect of being influenced by professional learning activities, which increases the teacher's performance. It can also be noticed that the overall goal orientation of teachers demonstrated the highest mediating effect of professional learning activities-at-work on teacher performance (PLA=.1970). This indirect effect means that respondents who differ by one unit in their reported professional learning activities-at-work are estimated to vary by 19.70% on the teacher's performance.

In relation with the present study, the result of the study conducted by Yean, et al., (2016) indicated that highly engaged academic staff members are more likely to display a higher degree of learning goal orientation, which in turn tends to engage in creative job behavior. The underlying theory received complete support from the discussions, which highlight learning goal orientation as a key mediator in explaining the relationship between creative work behavior and job engagement.

Table 19. Moderating Effect of Task Difficulty on the Relationship Between Professional Learning Activities at Work and Teachers' Performance.

Model Summary						
R	R-sq	MSE	F	df1	df2	P
.605	.366	.070	35.380	3.000	184.000	.000
Model	coeff	se	T	P	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	4.962	.557	8.914	.000	3.863	6.060
PLA	-.264	.158	-1.673	.096	-.575	.047
TDM	-1.453	.312	-4.654	.000	-2.069	-.837
Int 1	.366	.088	4.155	.000	.192	.540

Legend: PLA (Professional Learning Activities-at-work); GOT (Goal Orientation of Teachers); TP (Teacher's Performance).

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Table 19 shows the moderating effect of task difficulty to the relationship between professional learning activities-at-work and teachers' performance. Moderation analyses were initiated using PROCESS Macro v4.1 following Hayes's (2022) procedure. Findings revealed that constructs of task difficulty significantly moderate the relationship between professional learning activities at work and teacher performance. The results showed that task difficulty was estimated at 36.6% ($t=4.155$; $F=35.380$; $p=.000$) of the variation in the effect of professional learning activities at work on teacher performance.

It indicates if the teacher finds their task difficult, they will make their selves highly engaged in professional learning activities at work so that they will have high performance.

The findings that the respondents disagree that they find difficulty in their tasks in school, and they moderately engaged in participation in professional learning activities at work affect teachers' performance because the findings show that teachers have very satisfactory performance.

This study is related to the study conducted by Adler & Benbunan-Fich, (2014). The findings demonstrate that respondents who were required to multitask when the primary task was deemed difficult performed noticeably worse than both subjects who did not multitask and subjects who were free to multitask as they pleased. On the other hand, those who were made to multitask when the main activity was deemed easy performed noticeably better than both those who chose to multitask and those who did not.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings as summarized, the following are concluded:

First, teachers are moderately engaged in professional learning activities at work because of a lack of time in engaging at different professional activities. Meanwhile, they are highly engaged in terms of experimenting. They try new things for teaching and learning to happen effectively. Second teachers have a very satisfactory performance with regard to content, knowledge and pedagogy; learning environment and diversity of learners; curriculum and planning; assessment and reporting; community linkages and professional engagement; and personal growth and professional development. Third, teachers have a very high goal orientations at work. Fourth, on the level of difficulty of their task in school, teachers did not find difficulty in doing their task in school. They find it easy doing their task. Fifth, there is a significant relationship between professional learning activities at work and goal orientation of the teachers. Teachers engagement in professional learning activities at work affects their goal orientation. Sixth, there is a significant relationship between professional learning activities at work and teacher's performance. If teachers always engage in professional learning activities at work, they will have a high performance. Seventh, goal orientation of teachers is a significant mediator in the relationship between professional learning activities at work and teacher performance. Lastly, constructs of task difficulty significantly moderate the relationship between professional learning activities at work and teacher performance.

From the drawn conclusions, the following recommendations are formulated:

First, for the school to organize and conduct different professional learning activities that teachers may engage with and create professional development opportunities that promote teacher collaboration. Also, prioritize teachers' professional development that is tailored to their needs to continuously improve their teaching competencies to augment classroom instructions. Second, for the school administrators to give technical assistance and support teachers to engage in different professional learning activities. Provide teachers with constructive guidance using such feedback, improving teacher performance and resulting in greater student success. Give timely feedback to allow them to reflect on their practices and adjust while the classroom experience is still fresh in their minds. Third, for the teachers to find time to engage in different professional learning activities for them to keep-up to date and to collaborate. Continue to apply the different tasks with regard to their performance. Use information and communication technology to provide access to content, professional development and professional learning communities. Fourth, for future researchers to

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conduct similar studies, especially on teacher engagement on professional activities-at-work, and their relation to students' performance.

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